

ISOLATING, DIAGNOSING AND TREATING VARIOUS FUNGI THAT CAUSE CONTAMINATION OF THE INTERIOR SURFACES OF BATHROOMS. - BASRAH IRAQ

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Abstract: Different types of fungi causing contamination of bathrooms were isolated from five different houses and five informal buildings. After identifying and isolating the fungi, a locally made product was used as a fungicide to eliminate fungi and molds that cause biological degradation, paint destruction and bad odor in bathrooms.

Keywords: Candida, fungi, Alternaria alternate, walls, Institute, Aspergillus.

Introduction

Mold affects the appearance of the bathroom. Stains and color changes may appear on various surfaces, and a distinctive unpleasant odor is emitted when entering the bathroom. Furthermore, it damages plaster, wallpaper, paint and even furniture. This means that the residents of the house are exposed to additional costs associated with the purchase of new furniture, and sometimes a more expensive and comprehensive renovation may be necessary. (Gajdacs, M., Doczi, I., Abrok, M., Lazar, A. and Burian, K. (2019)). Some pathogenic fungi in soil and plants that can cause infection are transferred to people's homes by animals or human shoes. Fungi are usually very dangerous because of their ability to withstand harsh environmental conditions and can Bacteria survive low humidity. (Ayanbimpe, G.M., Danjuma, W.S. and Okolo, M.O. (2012)). Mold is classified as a fungus and often lives on shower walls, window sills and other places where moisture levels are high. It is usually in the form of a powder, thin and light in color, while other types of mold are thick and dark. In general, the health or property effects of mold are less severe than those caused by other types of mold. (mcrdsd.marines.mil/Portals) It has been reported that occupants of buildings in the indoor environment have fungal allergies and are affected by toxins produced by fungi. (Caillaud, D., , B, Keirsbulck, M. Leynaert. and Nadif, R. (2018). In addition to property damage, mold can impair the indoor air quality of your home and cause A variety of health problems for sensitive individuals, specifically asthma. Mold produces allergens and irritants that can cause nasal congestion, sore throat, coughing, burning eyes, or skin rashes. Inhaling or touching mold can cause allergic reactions. If you experience any symptoms. (Wing, S., Marshall, S. W. and Wilkosky, T. C. (2006). Molds play an important role in nature by breaking downorganic materials. We routinely encounter mold spores aspart of everyday life, in both outdoor and indoor environments. In most cases, the body's immune and respiratorysystems normally provide defense mechanisms that protect itfrom health effects of regular exposure to molds. (Robins, C. and Morell J. (2007). Diagnostics and treatment have improved, but death rates from invasive mold infections remain high. (Quan, C. and Spellberg, B. (2010). Eliminating fungi through chemical treatment using solutions is very important to create a good environment inside the home

or public buildings Fungicides are pesticides that kill or prevent the growth of fungi and their spores. (Jochen P. Zubrod).

Material & methods :

A-Material :

- 1-Petri dishes
- 2- Sabouraud's medium
- 3-Microscope
- 4-swab
- 5-slide & cover slide
- 6-incubater
- 7- Alcohol
- 8- Bernner
- 9- Wire Loope
- 10- D.W

B-Methods:

A-Sample collection :

Random samples were collected from public and home bathrooms and from university student bathrooms.

B- Sample cultivation:

Transfer the collected samples from the pigeons to plates containing SDA. Use sterile tools such as a swab to transfer specimens to dishes. Inoculate a group of plates to increase the chance of growth of the existing fungi.

C- Reproduction and incubation:

- 1- Place the dishes in a place suitable for fungal growth, such as incubation at an appropriate temperature. We were careful to avoid external contamination of the dishes during the incubation period.. Growth monitoring:
- 2- We monitored the dishes on a regular basis to watch the growth of fungi.
- 3- Record the results and document the growing fungi.

Result: Different types of fungi have been isolated from the interior surfaces of bathrooms in homes and public health facilities to search and investigate important types that may cause damage to the paint and an unpleasant odor in addition to appearance. The following results were achieved:

Type of fungi	house bath room no	building bathroom no
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	1,2,4,5	2,3
<i>Candida albicans</i>	1,2,3,5	1
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	1,2	5
<i>Penicillium</i>	4,5	2,3
<i>Alternaria alternate</i>	2	0

Table no (1) show Fungal species identified in homes and buildings

Dissuasion:

Table no (1) showed the presence of two common types of fungi in homes and buildings, namely (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*). *Aspergillus niger* was diagnosed in House No. 1 (1, 2, 4, 5) and (2, 3) in the buildings from the study samples. *Candida albicans* was diagnosed in House No. 1 (1, 2, 3, 5) and (1) in the buildings from the study samples. *Aspergillus flavus* was diagnosed in House No. (1, 2) and (5) in the buildings from the study samples

Penicillium was diagnosed in House No. (4,5) and (2,3) in the buildings from the study samples. *Alternaria alternate* was diagnosed in House No. (2) The study showed that the lowest percentage of presence of *Alternaria alternate* was only in one house, number 2. The study also showed that the spread of fungi in building bathrooms is less than in homes. This is due to ventilation, the size and area of bathrooms, and continuous cleaning with disinfectants and sterilizers. **Treatment:** A local product was made as a fungicide to get rid of the existing fungi. A chemical-phyto product that contains a group of effective substances that directly and very effectively eliminate fungi that cause biological degradation. **Product Ingredients:** Copper sulfate pentahydrate & Rosemary & MetatinGT & DW. How to use: Spray. **Odds, F.C. (1992)**

Before After

Table no. 2 Show Explain the use of the local product as a fungicide in fungal cultivation media

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